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Editorial Contact:

Anand Bihari
Kala Kunj, Besdide Canara Bank
Bazar Samiti Road, Bahadurpur
Patna-800016

Website : <http://satraachee.org.in>
E-mail : satraachee@gmail.com
Mob. : 9661792414 (A.Bihari.)
: 9415256226 (Kamlesh Verma.)

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Metadiscourse in Argumentative Texts: A Comparative Study of Languages and Humanities Domains

- Swadha Bhartiya¹
- Dr. Anil Sehrawat²
- R.C. Sharma³

Abstract:

Readers can connect, organize, interpret, and develop attitudes about the informational material with the help of metadiscourse. To express their opinions and interact with readers, language and humanities undergraduate and graduate students use a variety of metadiscourse elements; the study examined the quantitative differences in the use of metadiscourse elements to achieve coherence. The findings of the study reveal that ESL writers of these domains differ in the use of emphatics at undergraduate level and illocutionary markers and emphatics at postgraduate level.

Keywords: Metadiscourse, illocutionary markers, hedges, emphatics, connectives, narrators, attitude markers, commentary

Introduction:

Metadiscourse stands as a linguistic attribute that plays a crucial role in enhancing the coherence of a text. It's fundamentally understood that all writers direct their compositions toward an audience, and the utilization of metadiscourse serves as an effective bridge between the writer and their readers. "Metadiscourse" was originally introduced by Harris (1970), but it gained substantial prominence after being elaborated upon in Williams's (1981) work *Style: Ten Lessons in Clarity and Grace*. Williams aptly described metadiscourse as the act of "writing about writing," encompassing all aspects of textual expression that do not directly

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1. ***Swadha Bhartiya***, Amity Institute of English Studies & Research, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida, INDIA
 2. ***Anil Sehrawat***, Amity Institute of Corporate Communication, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida, INDIA
 3. ***R. C. Sharma***, Department of Linguistics, Delhi University, Delhi

pertain to the primary subject matter under discussion. He went on to elaborate that metadiscourse serves as a means of engaging with the reader and encompasses distinct categories: Sequencers and topicalizers (consequently, firstly, lastly) elucidate the organization of the text, facilitating a clearer understanding of its structure; while emphatics and hedges, ranging from expressions like “it is quite true that” to “it is unlikely that,” convey the writer’s certainty concerning the accuracy of the content. Another category, referred to as attributors and narrators, involves indicating the origin of concepts and information. This origin could stem from the writers themselves (based on my observations), external sources (in line with Chomsky’s perspective), or even society as a whole (as seen in observations made). These characteristics of metadiscourse effectively convey the intentions of writers, ultimately simplifying the process for readers to construct meaning from the text.

Approaching the subject from a slightly altered angle, Lautamatti (1978) examined the progression of discourse subjects within paragraphs and the demarcation of non-topical elements. These non-topical elements are highlighted through italics in the subsequent illustrations: Anthropologists *suggest* that human beings... and It is *evident* that children.... She posits the notion that these non-topical elements (features of metadiscourse) engage in interaction with the topical components, thereby contributing to the advancement of sentence flow in the discourse. Through a logical arrangement of topics, coherent texts emerge, while the incorporation of non-topical linguistic elements aids readers in comprehending the text.

Metadiscourse holds significance as it enables writers to connect with their readers and involve them in an evolving conversation. A secondary crucial role of metadiscourse is to enable writers to distinctly outline the text’s structure. This heightened textual structure awareness enhances cohesion by explicitly revealing the connections. In addition, the connections among sentences, paragraphs, and other textual elements become more evident. Moreover, writers who possess a comprehensive grasp of the significance and rhetorical purpose of metadiscourse indicators can spot imperfections in their evolving text. This ability, in turn, enhances the lucidity of their writing. Consequently, metadiscourse not only enhances the readability of an essay but also heightens the probability of effectively conveying the intended message.

As students embark on the writing process, they often direct their efforts towards what Porter (1992) has defined as a tangible audience—an actual individual who provides tangible reactions to their writing. Regrettably, the actual audience for students is frequently limited in scope—a teacher who prioritizes grammar and mechanics but may not be inherently invested in the textual concepts or the essay’s progression. This audience is typically not conducive to meaningful dialogue. Nonetheless, as students mature in their writing skills, they exhibit increased sophistication in considering their target audience. They aim to enhance the clarity of their ideas and exhibit a degree of concern regarding whether their prospective readers will grasp the intended message. These students progress in their journey as writers, they begin to exhibit a heightened awareness of crafting text that is more considerate and ultimately more reader friendly. This entails adhering to principles outlined by Anderson et al. (1980)

and Armbuster (1984), which emphasize enhancing the readability and efficiency of textual content. As writers progress in their development, they undergo a transformation into participants of a discourse community, consequently reflecting the community's principles and beliefs through their written manifestations.

The situation involving writers who are learning a second language (L2) is notably challenging. These individuals not only grapple with mastering the language itself, navigating through unfamiliar aspects like morphology, syntax, and vocabulary, but they also encounter the added complexity of adapting to the standards and practices of a second language discourse community. It is crucial to possess a command of the virtual system, specifically grammatical rules, it alone does not guarantee proficient writing. Like how L2 speakers must acquire the skills to construct grammatically correct sentences and utilize them fittingly within their linguistic group, writers need the ability to compose coherent English and comprehend the discourse conventions within their community. Achieving effective communication, whether spoken or written, relies on possessing a solid foundation of communicative competence.

Hence, there exists a curiosity in uncovering the advancements being made by young language learners in employing these attributes that aid readers in comprehending a text. As outlined by Werlich (1976), "a text is a prolonged arrangement of syntactic components like words, phrases, and clauses, accompanied by textual units that display both cohesion among the elements and a sense of entirety." The notions of coherence and completion form fundamental text grammatical principles that underlie the comprehension of the linguistic composition of texts.

Methodology

Objective

The study investigates the quantitative disparity in the utilization of metadiscourse to achieve coherence in the argumentative writings produced by students in the fields of languages and humanities.

Design

This study employs a descriptive research design to elucidate the aspects of the research problem pertaining to its "how," "what," "when," and "where" dimensions. The focal point of the study remains the exploratory nature, which guides the investigation process.

Data Collection Tool

The data analysis procedure involves the systematic inspection and evaluation of textual passages containing around two hundred words. The written compositions are authored by students who are actively engaged in the pursuit of undergraduate and postgraduate degrees within the fields of languages and humanities. The study's participants are exclusively enrolled in universities located within the National Capital Region (NCR) of India. The paragraphs were written on the topic "Are we too dependent on smartphones and computers?"

Data Collection Procedure

Students enrolled in both undergraduate and postgraduate programs within the languages

and humanities domains at universities located in the National Capital Region were approached to craft a two hundred words paragraph on the subject of “Are we too dependent on smartphones and computers?” A time frame of thirty minutes was allotted for composing these passages. Participation in the study was voluntary, and participants were provided with information regarding the study’s objectives and the intended utilization of the gathered information. A total of 287 written compositions were gathered from five distinct universities.

Analysis of the Data

After evaluating 287 texts, 197 complete and coherent spontaneous expository writings were identified for the subsequent research phase. These 197 texts were classified as either coherent or incoherent based on the reader-based approach, drawing from works by Lowe Davies (1998) and Galloway (2002). To accomplish this, two independent volunteers were engaged to read and categorize the texts. Each reader assigned coherence ratings on a scale of 1 to 5, utilizing separate sets of texts. Of these, 197 texts (comprising 56 from Languages UG, 38 from Languages PG, 47 from Humanities UG, and 56 from Humanities PG) were consistently rated 4 or 5 by both readers, rendering them coherent. These texts were then subjected to text analysis to explore the use of metadiscourse in spontaneous argumentative writings, specifically in fostering coherence. The analysis employed Vande Kopple’s (1985, 1997) classification: connectives, code glosses, illocutionary markers, narrators, emphatics, hedges, attitude markers, and commentary.

To assess quantitative disparities in the application of metadiscourse across both languages and humanities domains, a ‘t’ test was employed. This test aimed to ascertain variations in the utilization of metadiscourse within and between these domains.

Results

This study examines the variability in the use of metadiscourse features in argumentative essays written by undergraduate and postgraduate students in the disciplines of languages and humanities. The primary aim was to ascertain how academic discipline influences writing proficiency. Consequently, the study involves a comparison of students based on the application of metadiscourse elements to establish coherence in spontaneous argumentative texts. This comparison occurs both within the academic domain (UG and PG) and at the domain level (Languages and Humanities).

To conduct these comparisons, the ‘t’ test is employed. The test is used to assess groups within the same domain, such as Languages UG vs. Languages PG and Humanities UG vs. Humanities PG. Additionally, comparisons are made at the domain level: Languages UG vs. Humanities UG, Languages PG vs. Humanities PG, and the collective Languages UG+PG vs. Humanities UG+PG.

Initially, the analysis centers on intra-domain comparisons. For instance, the expository texts from the undergraduate and postgraduate levels within the Languages domain are juxtaposed. The ensuing outcomes are presented below:

Table 1: Metadiscourse in undergraduate and postgraduate texts of Language domain

Variables	Languages UG (56)		Languages PG (38)		t-ratio	P-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Connectives	0.41	0.75	0.57	0.82	-1.01	0.31
Code Glosses	0.76	0.78	0.44	0.55	2.17	0.03
Illocutionary Markers	0.26	0.52	0.23	0.43	0.30	0.76
Narrators	0.33	0.51	0.36	0.67	-0.23	0.81
Emphatics	1.10	0.73	1.36	0.81	-1.62	0.10
Hedges	2.69	1.32	2.28	1.33	1.46	0.14
Attitude Markers	0.05	0.22	0.10	0.31	-0.93	0.35
Commentary	0.03	0.18	0.02	0.16	0.25	0.80

Table 1 illustrates a notable disparity in the utilization of code glosses between undergraduate and postgraduate students in the field of languages. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that there is a lack of substantial distinction observed among these elements in terms of their utilization of connectives, illocutionary markers, narrators, emphatics, hedges, attitude markers, and commentary.

The utilization of code glosses in texts was found to be more prevalent among undergraduate students of languages in comparison to postgraduate students of language.

Table 2: Metadiscourse in undergraduate and postgraduate texts of Humanities domain

Variables	Humanities UG (47)		Humanities PG (56)		t-ratio	P-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Connectives	0.46	0.85	0.64	0.79	-1.07	0.28
Code Glosses	0.61	0.70	0.58	0.80	0.18	0.85
Illocutionary Markers	0.17	0.52	0.44	0.65	-2.32	0.02
Narrators	0.27	0.45	0.28	0.62	-0.08	0.93
Emphatics	0.74	0.76	0.98	0.84	-1.48	0.14
Hedges	2.72	1.44	2.66	1.46	0.21	0.82
Attitude Markers	0.12	0.33	0.10	0.31	0.32	0.74
Commentary	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.22	-1.61	0.10

Table 2 presents a comparative analysis indicating a considerable disparity in the utilization of illocutionary markers between undergraduate and postgraduate students enrolled in humanities programs. Nevertheless, there is a lack of substantial variation observed among the students within this field when it comes to their utilization of commentary, connectives, code glosses, narrators, emphatics, attitude markers, and hedges. Commentaries were not utilized by undergraduate students; however postgraduate students employed the use of commentaries.

The utilization of illocutionary markers in textual discourse was shown to be more prevalent among postgraduate students in the field of humanities, as opposed to their undergraduate counterparts.

Table 3: Metadiscourse in undergraduate texts of Languages and Humanities domains

Variables	Languages (56)		Humanities (47)		t-ratio	P-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Connectives	0.41	0.75	0.47	0.85	-0.36	0.36
Code Glosses	0.77	0.78	0.62	0.70	1.01	0.15
Illocutionary Markers	0.27	0.52	0.17	0.52	0.94	0.17
Narrators	0.34	0.51	0.28	0.45	0.65	0.25
Emphatics	1.11	0.73	0.74	0.76	2.45	0.00
Hedges	2.70	1.32	2.72	1.44	-0.09	0.46
Attitude Markers	0.05	0.22	0.13	0.33	-1.32	0.09
Commentary	0.04	0.18	0.00	0.00	1.30	0.09

According to the data presented in Table 3, there is a notable distinction among students within the Languages and Humanities category in terms of their utilization of emphatic expressions. Nonetheless, there is a lack of substantial disparity observed among the students across these domains in terms of their utilization of connectives, code glosses, illocutionary markers, narrators, hedges, attitude markers, and commentary.

The results suggest that students studying language employed a greater degree of emphasis in their texts compared to students studying humanities. The students of languages have incorporated commentary into their written works.

Table 4: Metadiscourse in postgraduate texts of Languages and Humanities domains

Variables	Languages (38)		Humanities (56)		t-ratio	P-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Connectives	0.58	0.82	0.64	0.79	-0.37	0.35
Code Glosses	0.45	0.55	0.59	0.80	-0.94	0.17
Illocutionary Markers	0.24	0.43	0.45	0.65	-1.72	0.04
Narrators	0.37	0.67	0.29	0.62	0.61	0.27
Emphatics	1.37	0.81	0.98	0.84	2.20	0.01
Hedges	2.29	1.33	2.66	1.46	-1.24	0.10
Attitude Markers	0.11	0.31	0.11	0.31	-0.02	0.48
Commentary	0.03	0.16	0.05	0.22	-0.63	0.26

Table 4 demonstrates a notable distinction in the utilization of illocutionary markers and emphatics between students belonging to the Languages and Humanities domains. Nevertheless, there is a lack of substantial disparity observed among the students across these domains in terms of their utilization of connectives, code glosses, narrators, hedges, attitude indicators, and comments.

The results suggest that students majoring in humanities demonstrated a higher frequency of illocutionary indicators in their written texts, while those majoring in language exhibited a greater prevalence of emphatic language usage.

Table 5: Metadiscourse in texts of Languages and Humanities domains

Variables	Language (94)		Humanities (103)		t-ratio	P-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Connectives	0.48	0.78	0.56	0.82	-0.73	0.23
Code Glosses	0.64	0.71	0.60	0.75	0.34	0.36
Illocutionary Markers	0.26	0.48	0.32	0.61	-0.82	0.20
Narrators	0.35	0.58	0.28	0.55	0.86	0.19
Emphatics	1.21	0.77	0.87	0.81	2.99	0.00
Hedges	2.53	1.33	2.69	1.44	-0.79	0.21
Attitude Markers	0.07	0.26	0.12	0.32	-0.99	0.16
Commentary	0.03	0.17	0.03	0.16	0.11	0.45

According to the data presented in Table 5, there is a substantial difference in the utilization of emphatics among students majoring in Language and Humanities. Nevertheless, the utilization of connectives, code glosses, illocutionary markers, narrators, hedges, attitude markers, and commentary does not exhibit any noteworthy disparity among the students belonging to these respective domains.

The results suggest that the language students employed a higher number of emphatics in their writings compared to the humanities students.

Conclusion

This study investigates the extent of variation in the utilization of metadiscourse elements within explanatory essays produced by undergraduate and postgraduate students specializing in the fields of languages and humanities. The main objective was to determine the impact of academic discipline on writing proficiency. Thus, the research entails a comparative analysis of students, focusing on the utilization of metadiscourse features to establish coherence in impromptu argumentative texts. This similarity is observed in both the academic sphere, encompassing undergraduate and postgraduate studies, and at the disciplinary level, namely within the fields of Languages and Humanities.

The findings of the study suggest a significant variation in the usage of coding glosses among undergraduate and postgraduate students within the domain of language studies. The frequency of code glosses in written texts was shown to be higher among undergraduate students studying languages as compared to postgraduate students specializing in language studies. One notable observation indicates a significant discrepancy in the usage of illocutionary markers among undergraduate and postgraduate students who are currently enrolled in humanities programs. The prevalence of illocutionary indicators in textual speech was found to be higher among postgraduate students in the humanities compared to their undergraduate peers. The students' ability to use metadiscourse improves as they progress to higher classes (Sehrawat, 2014).

One noteworthy disparity observed among students classified under the Languages and Humanities discipline pertains to their usage of emphatic language. Commentary has been integrated into the written works of language students. There exists a significant disparity in the use of illocutionary markers and emphatics among postgraduate students who are affiliated with the fields of Languages and Humanities. The students who are pursuing a humanities major displayed a larger occurrence of illocutionary indications in their written texts, whereas those majoring in language showed a higher prevalence of using emphatic language.

There exists a notable disparity in the usage of emphatics between students pursuing a major in Language and students pursuing a major in Humanities. It indicates that the academic discipline of students influences their writing skills (Bhartia, Sehrawat & Sharma, 2023).

In the context of instructing university students in the art of composing argumentative essays that involve presenting both sides of an issue, engaging in polemics, and similar techniques, it becomes imperative to incorporate multiple exemplar argumentative texts. These texts serve as models and starting points for student writers, while avoiding essays that excessively dwell on personal matters. Notably, a study revealed that the rhetorical prowess of English as a Second Language (ESL) writers exhibited a 50% increase when they composed essays in a home environment as opposed to within a classroom setting. This observation underscores the discernible advantages of take-home essays over those produced in a classroom setting (Kroll, 1990).

It is imperative to underscore that the process of identifying the suitable degree of metadiscourse utilization and the amount of writer/reader exposure in writing is not a straightforward task. These aspects demand more deliberate consideration within the ESL classroom. Achieving effective writing entails grasping language conventions, which are fundamental components of developing strong communication skills.

Supplying students with genuine and pertinent texts holds potential as a strategy to enhance their consciousness, as suggested by Gavioli (2005). The introduction of well-structured classroom discussions on these matters, considering their relationship to genre and, conceivably, culture, can likely lead to writing that is more organic, streamlined, and impactful.

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